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Research Article

**A CROSS-SECTIONAL RESEARCH TO ASSESS THE
KNOWLEDGE (GOOD, AVERAGE & POOR) & ATTITUDE
(POSITIVE & NEGATIVE) OF FEMALES TOWARDS
MENOPAUSE**¹Dr. Tahir Ahmad, ²Dr. Umer Munir, ³Dr. Muhammad Arslan Majeed¹The Indus Hospital / THQ Raiwind²Aziz Bhatti Shaheed Hospital DHQ Gujrat³THQ Hospital Shakargarh**Abstract:****Objectives:** Evaluation of knowledge and attitude of females regarding menopause.**Material and methods:** Present research was cross-sectional in its design. The place of this research was Gynecology and Obstetrics Department of Jinnah Hospital, Lahore (January to September 2017). Participants of the study were females (N=117). We evaluated knowledge and attitude regarding menopause.**Results:** Mean age of participants was (50.84 ± 3.03) years. Around 54.24% (96) were in the age of 51 – 55. Mean duration of disease and mean BMI was (4.78 ± 2.36) years (27.65 ± 3.70 kg/m²) respectively. Knowledge score means and attitude score mean was (14.89 ± 7.65), (4.57 ± 2.39) respectively. Results of this research indicate that 11.30% (20) participants have poor level knowledge, 46.89% (83) have a moderate level of knowledge, and 41.81% have good level knowledge. Moreover, research highlights that women have a positive and negative attitude regarding menopause which is 79.66% (141) participants and 20.34% (36) participants respectively.**Conclusion:** We concluded in our research that for providing the best level of information and support to women health caregivers recognize the attitudes of women and expectations about menopause.**Keywords:** Knowledge, Menopause, Attitude, Negative and Positive.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Tahir Ahmad,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Menopause is means women cannot conceive and stops menstruating, it is part of her life cycle. Typical (mean) age of this is fifty-one years [1]. Unequal menstruation and next to menopause are warm flushes, skin dryness and vaginal dryness are symptoms of menopause. Few women may go through physical as well as emotional signs. Owing to the age of the woman, education, parity, status of hormones, culture, geographical, and economic status attitude and knowledge regarding menopause may show variance [2]. Women should recognize the transition in menopause and convert it into useful knowledge. A research indicates in Botswana that it is the duty of gynaecologists and obstetrician to give knowledge of transitions in menopause each visiting women [3]. Significant variances are present in attitude regarding menopause owing to the background of education, uneducated women show better attitude (positive) than educated women. Likewise, significant variances are present in symptoms of menopause and attitude in menopausal position (status). Women in premenopausal status feel a maximum symptom of menopause as compared to pre and post-menopause women and women in post-menopause exhibit positive attitude as compared to pre and perimenopausal women [4]. A Turkish research highlights that among surveyed (90.70%) women perceive menopause as the end of youth, (85.5%) perceive as the start of old age, and (97.6%) perceive it as the end of productiveness [5]. A research highlights that (68.51%) female goes through extreme sweating and warm flushes, (37.7%) feel vagina dryness and (30.7%) experience sexual difficulties. Around (57.5%) women show anxieties with menopause and (47.9%) reject the psychological and bodily effects by menopause [6]. To evaluate the knowledge and attitude of females related to menopause was the rationale of present research. There are some debatable studies present even in local researches. By focusing on this research findings, we can manage general awareness program regionally as well as nationally for the education of women regarding menopause. These educational programs and guided training activities are helpful in maintaining healthy and active lives that will enhance knowledge and change the attitude regarding menopause.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The present research was cross-sectional in its design. The place of this research was Gynecology and Obstetrics Department of Jinnah Hospital, Lahore (January to September 2017). Overall one hundred and seventy-seven (177) women visit Outpatient gynaecology having symptoms related to

post menopause i.e., insomnia which is loss of sleep, mazodynia which is breast pain, weight increase, headache, warm flushes (sensation of intense hotness with sweating and speedy heartbeat and may last from 2-30 minutes for every incidence). We selected the menopause of > 1 years, the age of 45 to 55 years, parity 1 to 5. We did not include patients of Psychological disorder (on clinical assessment), Gynecological Malignancy (medical history), and patients having a Thyroid disorder (TSH > 5mIU/L). Before the research, we obtained consent form from each participant. We also noted the demographic information like age, name, parity, contact number and address. We have a questionnaire to know the level of knowledge and attitude of women and then entered all the data on the predesigned form.

Operational Definitions:

Menopause: End of menstruating by a woman since last two years of age group 45 to 55.

Knowledge: We measured it with the help of a questionnaire (26 question). Response option to these questions was right and wrong. Right answers have 1 score and wrong have 0 scores. On these responses and scores, there are 3 classifications of knowledge of people i.e., “poor knowledge” with score 0 to 9, “Average knowledge” with a score >9 to 17 and “Good knowledge” with score >17-26.

Attitude: We measured it with the help of a questionnaire (10 question). Response option to these questions was “agreed” and “disagreed”. The agreed response has 1 score and disagreed responses have 0 scores. On these responses and scores, there are 2 classifications of attitude i.e., negative attitude with a score of 0 to 5, positive attitude with a score > 5 to 10. We register the data on SPSS and analyzed on it. We calculated the mean and standard deviation (SD) of quantitative variables e.g., BMI, age, parity, menopause duration, a score of knowledge and attitude. We calculated the frequency and percentage of qualitative variables e.g., parity, body mass index (BMI) (< 27kg / m²/> 27 kg /m²), level of knowledge i.e., poor, average, good and attitude i.e., positive and negative regarding menopause. We did stratification and post-stratification for effect modifiers e.g., menopause duration, age, BMI (< 27kg / m²/> 27 kg /m²), parity to look for their impact on knowledge and attitude. Significant Value of p was ≤0.05.

RESULTS:

Mean age of participants was (50.84 ± 3.03) years. Around 54.24% (96) were in the age of 51-55. Mean duration of disease and mean BMI was (4.78 ± 2.36) years (27.65 ± 3.70 kg/m²) respectively. Knowledge score means and attitude score mean was (14.89 ±

7.65), (4.57 ± 2.39) respectively. Mean parity score was (3.20 ± 1.34) . Results of this research indicate that 11.30% (20) participants have poor level knowledge, 46.89% (83) have a moderate level of knowledge, and 41.81% have good level knowledge. Moreover, research highlights that women have a positive and negative attitude regarding menopause which is 79.66% (141) participants and 20.34% (36) participants respectively. Results of this research indicate that 11.30% (20) participants have poor level knowledge, 46.89% (83) have a moderate level of knowledge, and 41.81% have good level knowledge. We did stratification of the level of knowledge with respect to menopause duration, age, BMI, and parity. There are two age groups 45 to 50 and 51 to 55 years. There were 45.76% (81) participants in the age group 46 to 50, and level of knowledge was poor with 13.58% in eleven participants, average with 41.98% in thirty-four participants, and good with 44.44% in thirty-six participants. There were 54.24% (96) participants in group 51 to 55 years and level of knowledge was poor with 9.38% in nine participants, average with 51.04% in forty-nine participants, and

good with 39.58% in thirty-eight participants. There is an insignificant relation between the level of knowledge and age groups which was $(P=0.426)$. Overall 57.63% (102) are with ≤ 5 years of menopause and 12.75% (13) participants having a poor level of knowledge about menopause then 45.10% (46) participant having average level knowledge, and 42.16% (43) participant have a good level of knowledge. Among seventy-five participants 42.37% participant have menopause duration of >5 years, seven with 9.33% participants have a poor level of knowledge, thirty-seven with 49.33% participant have an average level of knowledge, and thirty-one with 41.33% participant have a good level of knowledge. Statistically, there is an insignificant correlation among knowledge level and menopause duration ($p=0.734$). Overall ninety-nine with 55.93% are with BMI of ≤ 27 kg/m² and level of knowledge was poor in twelve having 12.12% participant, the average level of knowledge in forty-one with 41.41% participants, and good level of knowledge in forty-six with 46.46% participants.

Table – I: Knowledge and Attitude Among Participants

Knowledge and Attitude		Number	Percentage
Knowledge	Good	74	42
	Average	83	47
	Poor	20	11
Attitude	Positive	141	80
	Negative	36	20

Table – II: Stratification of Knowledge (Number and Percentage)

Variables		Poor		Average		Good		Total		P-Value
		No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	
Age (Years)	45 – 50	11	13.58	34	41.98	36	44.44	81	45.76	0.426
	51 – 55	9	9.38	49	51.04	38	39.58	96	54.24	
Menopause Duration (Years)	≤ 5	13	12.75	46	45.10	43	42.16	102	57.63	0.734
	> 5	7	9.33	37	49.33	31	41.33	75	42.37	
BMI (kg/m ²)	≤ 27	12	12.12	41	41.41	46	46.46	99	55.93	0.254
	> 27	8	10.26	42	53.85	28	35.89	78	44.07	
Parity	Para – I	3	12.00	9	36.00	13	52.00	25	14.12	0.089
	Para – II	2	6.45	14	45.16	15	38.39	31	17.51	
	Para – III	7	17.03	17	41.46	17	41.46	41	23.16	
	Para – IV	3	6.98	18	41.86	22	51.16	43	24.29	
	Para – V	5	13.51	25	67.57	7	18.92	37	20.93	

Among seventy-eight with 44.07% participant have BMI >27 kg/m², overall eight with 10.26% participants have a poor level of knowledge, forty-two with 53.85% participants have an average level of knowledge, and twenty-eight with 35.89% participants have a good level of knowledge. Insignificant correlation of BMI with the level of knowledge was present (p=0.254). Twenty-five (14.12%) participants were para (1) then thirty-one (17.51%) participants were para (2), Forty-one (23.16%) participants were para (3), Forty-three (24.29) participants were para (4) and thirty-seven (20.93) participants were para-(5). In para (1) participants level of knowledge was poor in three (12%) participants, average level of knowledge in fourteen (45.16%) participants, and good level of knowledge in fifteen (38.39%) participants, in seven (17.03%), seventeen (41.46%) and seventeen (41.46%) para (3) participant , in three (6.98%), eighteen (41.86%) and twenty-two (51.16%) para (4) participants and in five (13.51%), twenty-

five (67.57%) and seven (18.92%) para (5) participants. Parity and level of knowledge have an insignificant correlation ($p=0.089$). In 45 to 50 age group among eighty-one (45.76%) participants sixty-one (75.31%) participants have a positive attitude and twenty (14.69%) participants have a negative attitude. In 51 to 55 age group among ninety-six (54.24%) participants eighty (83.33%) have a positive attitude and sixteen (16.67%) have a negative attitude. There was an insignificant correlation among attitude and age group having $p=0.186$. In one hundred two (57.63%) participant have ≤ 5 menopause duration, seventy-nine (77.45%) participants have a positive attitude and twenty-three (22.25%) participants have a negative attitude. Among seventy-five (42.37%) participants with > 5 years menopause duration, sixty-two (82.67%) participant have a positive attitude and thirteen (17.33%) have a negative attitude. Between menopause duration and attitude, there is an insignificant correlation ($p=0.394$). Overall ninety-nine (55.93%) participants are with BMI of ≤ 27 kg/m² and in them, seventy-seven (77.78%) participants have a positive attitude and twenty-two (22.22%) participants have a negative attitude. In seventy-eight (44.07%) participant having BMI of > 27 kg/m², sixty-four (82.05%) participants have a positive attitude and fourteen (17.95%) have a negative attitude. BMI have an insignificant correlation with attitude ($p=0.483$). Positive attitude was present in nineteen (76.0%), twenty-two (70.97%), thirty-two (82.93%), thirty-six (82.72%) and thirty (81.08%) participants in para (1), para (2), para (3), para (4) and para (5). Insignificant ($P =0.662$) correlation between parity and attitude was present.

Table – III: Stratification of Attitude (Number and Percentage)

Variables		Positive		Negative		Total		P-Value
		No	%	No	%	No	%	
Age (Years)	45 – 50	61	75.31	20	14.69	81	45.76	0.426
	51 – 55	80	83.33	16	16.67	96	54.24	
Menopause Duration (Years)	≤ 5	79	77.45	23	22.55	102	57.63	0.734
	> 5	62	82.67	13	17.33	75	42.37	
BMI (kg/m ²)	≤ 27	77	77.78	22	22.22	99	55.93	0.254
	> 27	64	82.05	14	17.95	78	44.07	
Parity	Para – I	19	76.00	6	24.00	25	14.12	0.089
	Para – II	22	70.97	9	29.03	31	17.51	
	Para – III	34	82.93	7	17.07	41	23.16	
	Para – IV	36	82.72	7	16.28	43	24.29	
	Para – V	30	81.08	7	18.92	37	20.93	

DISCUSSION:

The aim of the present research was to evaluate the knowledge and attitude of women for menopause. Mean age of participants was (50.84 ± 3.03) years. Around 54.24% (96) were in the age of 51-55. Most of the participant ninety-six (54.24%) fall in age from 51 to 55. Most of the participant's ninety-six (54.24%) having age from 51 to 55 years. Difference do exist in defining the accurate age of menopause that occurs naturally, mean the beginning of menopause was (45.5) years [7]. Different researches indicate variability in age of menopause e.g., in Norway, it was 50.9 years, in Mayan female, it was 44.3 years, in Nigeria, it was forty-eight years [8]. Findings of our research indicate that twenty (11.30%) participants have a poor level of knowledge, eighty-three (46.89%) have a moderate level of knowledge, and seventy-four (41.81%) have a good level of knowledge. Present research indicates that one hundred and forty-one (79.66%) females have a positive attitude and thirty-six (20.34%) have a negative attitude regarding menopause. In a research by Malik HS said that around ninety-seven percent women had listened to the word of menopause and around 29.4% know symptoms. Most of the participants have positive attitude i.e., forty-seven percent concerning menopause [9]. Nusrat et. al., reported that around 15.8% of females know the effects and signs of menopause, 78.79% females regard menopause a naturally occurring process, 21.2% think it is an illness, 83.42% feel happiness regarding the stoppage of menses and they don't desire that menses to happen again, and 16.57% desire to have menses again [10]. Noroozi et. al., showed that eight percent participants have a poor level of knowledge, sixty-eight percent have a moderate level of knowledge and 38.5% have a good level of knowledge [11]. Moreover, regarding menopause 81.5% females have a positive attitude and 18.5% have negative. Investigator who belongs to Bahrain discovered that widowed and divorced female have a most positive attitude for menopause [12]. They must have such kind of attitude because their view is not bothering anyone [12]. It is highlighted that wives show positive attitude as compared to their husbands [13]. Mean age in a research was (47.44) years having median age of forty-eight years. Pattern of menstrual ending and education are only factors which have significant correlation with age at menopause. Around 93.4% have listened to the name of menopause, around 56.6% have some background knowledge regarding symptoms of menopause. Around forty-seven present females have a positive view regarding the end of menopause, around 85.8% regard menopause as naturally occurring [14]. In a research fifty-one

percent woman had a poor level of knowledge about menopause, balance highlighted their knowledge regarding menopause was good (29%), very good (17%), and excellent (2%) [15]. We can formulate very conveniently that direct exposure with menopause is necessary for attitude because women who haven't gone through this phase are fearful regarding what to look for in menopause. Post-menopausal females had experienced the menopausal phase and are less prone to false beliefs. Women who have gone past that phase feel less anxieties as compared to before this phase.

CONCLUSION:

We concluded in our research that for providing the best level of information and support to women health caregivers recognize attitudes of women and expectations about menopause.

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